

Stretch(Scale) Transformations and Quantum to Classical Transition Part 2

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In (1), a stretch transformation $T(x,p) \rightarrow (\sqrt{b}x, \sqrt{b}p)$, where b is a parameter from 1 to infinite is introduced. The main argument seems to be that if this transformation on the Wigner(x,p) semiclassical distribution, defined by (2) $1/(3.14\hbar) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy \exp(i2py) W(x+y)W(x-y)$, where W is the quantum wavefunction, then for $b \gg 1$, Wigner(x,p) is guaranteed to be positive (i.e. quantum effects have been removed) and one has achieved a classical statistical type of situation. We describe this a classical statistical type of situation because it is not the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann statistical result overall for any potential $V(x)$. If one uses a free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, one has Wigner(x,p)=1 which yields a constant density regardless of p . It seems, however, that one should be able to apply this to any bound classical state, i.e. any $V(x)$. In such a case, one breaks the x -axis into dx pieces such that one has a different $V=\text{constant}$ in each. Then one has a free particle solution in each dx . Thus, p from the Wigner(p,x) would then correspond to the appropriate p of each dx .

According to (2), the only one-dimensional Wigner(x,p) function which is guaranteed to be positive everywhere is the Gaussian in x with coefficient in the exponent linked with a p . This, incidentally, is the solution of the ground state quantum oscillator. We would like the solution, however, to apply to any bound state. To do so, we imagine that each dx is again considered to be large and maps to an oscillator ground state with a different spring constant. In other words, the leading term of an x power expansion of any $V(x)$ is removed and only the second term retained. We suggest that this may be an interpretation of Wigner(x,p) being always positive instead of thinking of a Gaussian wavepacket at each dx corresponding to a p as the oscillator ground state shows how the microscopic p states are completely random.

Wigner(x,p) Semiclassical Distribution

The Wigner(x,p) semiclassical distribution is defined by (2) as:

$$1/(3.14\hbar) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy \exp(i2py) W(x+y)W(x-y),$$

where W is the quantum wavefunction. For $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$, the free particle solution, Wigner(p,x) =1 regardless of p . We suggest that one may apply this to any bound state by considering each dx to have a different constant V . Then, each p value corresponds to a different dx and one has free motion in each dx , but then a jump in energy and p when the particle is in the next dx . We apply this kind of reasoning to a more general solution of Wigner(x,p).

Arguments of (1)

As noted in Part I, (1) introduces a stretch transformation such that:

$$T(x,p) = (\sqrt{b}x, \sqrt{b}p) \quad (2)$$

Here b is a parameter between 1 and infinite.

The key argument of (1) seems to be that if one applies this stretch transformation to Wigner(x,p), then for $b \gg 1$, Wigner(x,p) is always >0 . In other words, quantum features disappear and one achieves a classical result.

In (2) it is stated that the only one dimensional solution for Wigner(x,p) that is always positive is the Gaussian:

$$\exp(-axx+bx +c) \quad \text{where presumably } p \text{ is found in the coefficients } ((3))$$

As a result, it seems that the result obtained by (1) must match ((3)) in one dimension. Now ((3)) is the ground state solution of a quantum oscillator, but we desire a result which holds for any potential $V(x)$.

Using the reasoning of the first section, we map p in Wigner(x,p) to each dx , i.e. p is the classical p in:

$$pp/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

We now consider each dx to be large and represent the ground state of quantum oscillator with the spring constant adjusted for each dx to yield the correct p and E within dx . In other words, one replaces free particle motion with the ground state of quantum oscillator. This means that one considers an $x=0$ origin in each dx and expands $V(x) = a_1x+a_2xx$, but removes the a_1x . This, we argue, is no worse than considering a constant $v(x)$ in each dx which changes with dx . Here the spring constant changes instead.

We argue that one needs to consider dx regions because there is already an overall classical spatial distribution for x given by:

$$P(x) dx = C dt = Cdx/|v(x)| \quad \text{where } p=mv(x) \text{ nonrelativistically. } ((4b))$$

This has nothing to do with a Gaussian and a quantum $W^*(x)W(x)$ in the high energy level limit has crests such that an envelope function will roughly yield ((4b)). These ideas are unrelated to the Wigner(x,p) and so one needs to somehow map the Wigner(x,p) to the case of all $V(x)$.

The solution ((3)) is physically that of a quantum oscillator ground state.

The special feature of this solution is that $W(x)*W(x)$ is a Gaussian in x , while $\phi(p)*\phi(p)$ (where $\phi(p)$ is the Fourier transform of W) is a Gaussian in p . This is a special form for which quantum mechanical densities match classical statistical mechanical ones. One may see from $\phi(p)=\exp(-3.14*3.14 bb pp)$, that one has random weights for p in scattering. This is usually not the case in quantum mechanics because the potential introduces bias, whereas in classical mechanics, two particle scattering is completely random at each x . The potential there is deterministic and governs how a particle changes from one x to another, i.e. classically the

spatial density changes at each x . For the oscillator, one has classically $\exp(-1/bb xx)$ which matches the quantum case.

Thus, the ground state oscillator solution exhibits a decoupling of p and x and complete randomness which is usually not found in quantum mechanics.

As a result, the Wigner(x,p) being positive everywhere and being a Gaussian in one dimension matches the idea of quantum features disappearing as advocated by (1) (on the basis of Wigner(x,p) being positive alone).

We suggest that one must also show that microscope p values creating the wavefunction are random in order to really argue for the elimination of quantum effects, but this appears to be equivalent to Wigner(p,x) being positive everywhere.

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) introduces a stretch transformation $T(x,p)=(\sqrt{b}x, \sqrt{b}p)$ where b is a parameter from 1 to infinite. This transformation is applied to the Wigner(x,p) and it is argued that for $b \gg 1$, Wigner(x,p) is always positive.

According to (2), in the one dimensional case, the only solution for Wigner(x,p) that is always positive is the Gaussian $\exp(-axx+bx+c)$. Thus, we argue that the solution $b \gg 1$ of (1) in one dimension must be equivalent to a Gaussian.

The question is then how to interpret various classical $V(x)$ potential solutions which clearly do not have a Gaussian probability distribution. In particular, they are linked with $P(x)dx = Cdx/|v(x)|$. We suggest that instead of thinking of each dx as representing free motion $v(x)=\text{constnat}$, with $v(x)$ changing in each dx , that one consider the ground state of an oscillator in each dx . The spring constant is adjusted in each dx to produce the correct energy. This then leads to microscopic p values which are completely random because $W(x)=\exp(-bbxx)$ and its Fourier transform is $\exp(-3.14*3.14/bb pp)$ (3). In other words, the microscopic p 's are distributed in a completely random manner suggesting the removal of quantum effects. The ground state oscillator form is the only one for which both the quantum $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $\phi^*(p)\phi(p)$ match the classical result, but we argue that one can only apply this reasoning to dx units with spring constant adjustments for each dx .

References

- 1.Carcassi, G. and Landini, M. and Aidala, C Classical Mechanics as the high entropy limit of quantum mechanics Nov. 1, 2024 Semantic scholar
- 2.https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wigner_quasiprobability_distribution
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_harmonic_oscillator